

Image Reconstruction in Ultrasonography: A Literature Review

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Abstract— Medical imaging has become an indispensable tool in clinical diagnosis, driven by advances in physics applied to medicine. In this context, various imaging modalities—based on ionizing and non-ionizing radiation—have been developed from different physical principles, enabling the generation of images with specific characteristics and resolutions. Among these techniques, ultrasonography (US) stands out for using high-frequency sound waves to produce real-time images. Therefore, this work aims to present a literature review focused on image reconstruction methods applied to ultrasonography. For this purpose, articles published in English between 2020 and April 2025 were selected from databases such as PubMed, ScienceDirect, and Google Scholar. The analysis covered the physical principles of image formation, beamforming techniques, signal conversion processes, and processing algorithms used to enhance the quality of the resulting images, highlighting recent advances in the field and their impact on clinical practice.

Keywords — *Medical Imaging, Ultrasonography, Image Reconstruction.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Medical imaging has become an essential tool in clinical diagnosis, driven by advances in physics applied to medicine. In this context, various imaging modalities, based on both ionizing and non-ionizing radiation, have been developed from distinct physical principles, enabling the acquisition of images with specific characteristics of contrast, resolution, and depth [1].

The choice of the most appropriate imaging technique depends on multiple factors, such as the organ under evaluation and the nature of the clinical suspicion. It is therefore necessary to consider parameters like sensitivity, specificity, and the inherent risks associated with each method. Moreover, the effectiveness of medical imaging lies not only in its visual quality but also in the accuracy of its interpretation, emphasizing the importance of skilled professionals and the integration of technology with clinical expertise [1].

The ultrasonography (US) is a imaging technique that uses high-frequency sound waves emitted and received by a

transducer to generate real-time images of the body's internal structures. As these waves propagate through tissues, they are reflected at interfaces between regions with different acoustic impedances, producing echoes that are converted into electrical signals and subsequently transformed into two-dimensional or three-dimensional images. Since it does not involve ionizing radiation, US is considered a safe modality and is widely used in pregnant women, children, and for serial examinations, besides offers advantages such as low cost, portability, and broad availability in healthcare settings [2].

Its ability to produce dynamic, real-time images makes ultrasound particularly advantageous in obstetric, musculoskeletal, abdominal, and vascular evaluations. However, the technique also presents limitations, including reduced penetration into deep structures, interference from tissues containing air or bone, and a strong dependence on the operator's skill in both image acquisition and interpretation [2].

Although ultrasound is widely used in clinical practice, the imaging process is subject to various physical and technical variables. These factors necessitate the use of diverse processing methods to ensure images of adequate diagnostic quality. In this context, the integration of computational approaches with clinical practices becomes essential to enhance the accuracy and reliability of examinations—an issue explored and discussed throughout this literature review.

Given this scenario, the objective of this work is to conduct a bibliographic review of the image reconstruction processes in ultrasonography. To this end, scientific articles addressing image reconstruction techniques in ultrasound were selected, with the goal of providing a comprehensive overview of technological advancements in the field. Additionally, the review discusses the basic principles of imaging physics, ultrasonic beamforming techniques, signal conversion processes, and, finally, computational processing methods.

Articles were searched in PubMed and ScienceDirect for English-language studies published between 2020 and April 2025. The final selection was based on strict relevance to ultrasound image reconstruction techniques and direct applicability to this review's objectives.

The search was structured based on the following keywords and combinations: ("signal reconstruction" OR "signal processing") AND (ultrasonography OR "ultrasound imaging") AND ("image formation" OR "two-dimensional imaging" OR "2D image formation").

First, the PubMed portal was used for the initial results, according to the established criteria, and 8 results were obtained. The same process was then conducted on the LILACS portal, but this did not yield any results.

The same criteria were also applied in Google Scholar; however, more than 4,000 results were presented. Due to this, the modifier "*allintitle*" was used to ensure a more targeted search, which resulted in only one article being found.

Finally, the same methods were also used in the ScienceDirect database, with the addition of a specific open-access filter, and this search yielded 30 additional results.

In addition to the systematic searches, articles previously known by the contributors of this review were also considered, which, due to their relevance and alignment with the theme, were incorporated into the set of texts evaluated.

Therefore, after the initial selection of 39 potentially relevant articles, the Rayyan platform was used to identify duplicates, followed by a manual screening of the remaining papers according to their applicability to this review. In addition to the systematically retrieved studies, a small number of articles previously known by the authors were incorporated, as they directly addressed aspects of ultrasound image reconstruction not fully covered by the systematic search. These works were mainly used to provide well-established background information and were considered complementary rather than a substitute for the systematic process. At the end of this procedure, 11 articles were selected — 4 obtained from systematic searches — to compose this literature review, as shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Selection of Articles.

For the purposes of this literature review, the selected articles were classified into five thematic areas: the physics of ultrasound image formation, beamforming techniques, signal processing for image reconstruction, image display modes, and advances in image post-processing techniques.

A. Physics of Ultrasound Image Formation

According to the study by Grogan and Mount [3], the formation of ultrasound images is based on the interaction of high-frequency mechanical waves with biological tissues. These ultrasonic waves are generated by piezoelectric transducers, which convert electrical energy into mechanical pulses through the piezoelectric effect. To propagate through tissues, these pulses undergo multiple physical phenomena such as reflection, refraction, scattering, absorption, and attenuation, which are fundamental to the formation of the ultrasound image.

Among these phenomena, reflection plays a central role in image formation. This is because, when the waves encounter interfaces between tissues with different acoustic impedances — a parameter defined as the product of tissue density and the speed of sound — part of the energy is reflected as echoes and returns to the transducer, while the other part continues to propagate through the tissue. Thus, the amount of reflected energy is directly related to the impedance difference between media. The greater this difference, the more intense the reflection, generating greater contrast in the image.

Based on the reflected echoes, it also becomes possible to estimate the depth of structures through the time-of-flight, which corresponds to the interval between the emission of the pulse and the return of the echo. For this estimation, an average sound propagation speed in soft tissues of approximately 1,540 m/s is assumed. After that, the data are processed by algorithms that convert them into visual representations, usually in B-mode (Brightness), where the intensity of the echoes is mapped at different spatial positions, forming the two-dimensional image.

Furthermore, it is possible to observe that the quality of the obtained image is directly influenced by the wave frequency. Higher frequencies provide greater spatial resolution but lower penetration, making them appropriate for evaluating superficial structures. On the other hand, lower frequencies penetrate deeper but result in images with less detail.

Another relevant aspect to consider is the attenuation of ultrasonic waves as they propagate through tissues. This occurs because, along their path, part of the wave energy is gradually lost, mainly due to absorption and scattering effects. As a result, the higher the wave frequency and the deeper the structure being analyzed, the greater the energy loss tends to be, which may subsequently compromise the quality of the generated image.

To compensate for this effect and preserve image quality, some modern systems employ techniques such as Time Gain Compensation (TGC). In this regard, recent studies, such

as that of Civale et al. [4], have developed quantitative methods to estimate the in vivo attenuation coefficient using segmentation algorithms based on echo amplitude. The goal is to reduce variability caused by tissue heterogeneity and enhance the acoustic characterization of tissues.

Finally, it is important to highlight that beamforming is essential for the focusing and reception of echoes, directly influencing the resolution and accuracy of the image. Therefore, the principles and techniques associated with this process will be discussed in detail in Section B. Additionally, the presence of ultrasonographic artifacts, such as acoustic shadows, reverberations, and speckle noise, can compromise clinical interpretation. Thus, to mitigate these effects and improve image quality, processing techniques are applied, a topic that will be addressed in Section E.

B. Beamforming techniques

The Beamforming is a fundamental process in medical ultrasound, being responsible both for shaping the spatial distribution of the pressure field in the volume of interest and for recombining the received ultrasound signals to form diagnostic images. According to the practical guide of Demi [5], there is no single technique that is ideal for all applications. The choice of the most appropriate approach depends on a number of interdependent factors, such as spatial and temporal resolution, contrast, depth of penetration, array aperture and field of view size. The balance between these parameters defines the final performance of the imaging system and guides the type of *beamforming* to be used.

Göbl's review [6] describes various strategies for receive beamforming, among which is the traditional Delay-and-Sum (DAS) method. This technique consists of applying time delays to the signals received by each transducer element in order to align them temporally, such that their summation reinforces the contributions from a specific point within the tissue. DAS is simple, efficient, and easy to implement digitally; however, it still presents limitations regarding lateral resolution and artifact suppression, particularly in regions with low signal coherence or high noise levels.

In order to overcome these limitations, coherence-based techniques have been proposed, such as the Coherence Factor (CF). This technique computes the ratio between the coherent energy (i.e., the sum of the signals) and the total energy (i.e., the sum of the individual signal energies), assigning higher weights to regions where the received signals are more coherent. CF can be used in combination with Delay-and-Sum (DAS) to suppress sidelobes and enhance contrast, proving particularly useful in environments with interference or scattering.

Among the most innovative methods is the Short-Lag Spatial Coherence (SLSC) technique, which relies on the spatial correlation between pairs of elements in the array separated by short distances. This correlation is accumulated over multiple neighboring pairs, producing an image where regions of higher coherence appear brighter. SLSC has proven effective in reducing noise and improving contrast, especially under challenging clinical conditions such as hepatic or breast imaging.

Another powerful strategy is Delay Multiply and Sum (DMAS), which performs cross-multiplications between signals received by different elements to emphasize only the coherent and common contributions among them. The resulting product is then converted into a positive signal and passed through a bandpass filter. This approach enhances structural details and improves contrast by suppressing incoherent signals and interference; however, it has high computational cost and is therefore often suggested for use in scenarios with lower processing demand.

Finally, the adaptive Minimum Variance (MV) method formulates the beamforming task as an optimization problem, seeking a weight vector that minimizes the variance of the received signal (i.e., noise and interference) while preserving unity gain in the desired direction. This allows for more precise focusing and a significant improvement in spatial resolution, albeit at the expense of increased computational demands.

Each of these techniques represents a significant advancement over conventional Delay-and-Sum (DAS), offering specific improvements depending on the type of imaging desired or the clinical challenge being addressed. Thus, the choice among them should consider the trade-off between image quality, computational requirements, and the anatomical or functional characteristics of the region under investigation.

C. Signal Processing for Image Reconstruction

After beamforming and the acquisition of ultrasonic echoes, the received signals go through a series of processing steps before the final image is generated. As shown in Figure 2, this stage is responsible for filtering, detecting, and compressing the signals for subsequent processing, ensuring the visual quality required for clinical interpretation.

Fig. 2. Basic Mid-End Image Reconstruction Workflow. Adapted from Ali et al. [7].

As presented by Ali, Magee, and Dasgupta [7], the first operation performed is signal filtering — a fundamental step to enhance signal detectability. Using band-pass filters, the system removes noise components and isolates the frequency bands of interest, for example, to separate the fundamental or second harmonic spectrum. This process improves the signal-to-noise ratio and contributes to better spatial resolution in the final image.

After filtering, the signal must be processed to extract relevant information, which is done through envelope

detection. The Hilbert transform technique is commonly used to generate an analytical representation of the signal, making it possible to obtain its instantaneous amplitude regardless of the signal's frequency or mode of operation. This step is crucial because it converts the complex signal into a simplified form that can be visualized and interpreted in the final image.

Next, the processed signals undergo logarithmic compression. Due to the wide dynamic range of echo amplitudes, compression is necessary to fit the data into the grayscale range displayed on clinical monitors. This operation ensures that subtle differences between tissues with varying acoustic properties are appropriately visualized, preventing extreme intensities from dominating the image.

In addition to conventional procedures, there is the technique of frequency compounding, which consists of combining signals derived from multiple frequencies or modes of operation. As illustrated in Figure 3, the processing involves applying specific filters for each frequency band, followed by detection and compression of each signal. Subsequently, the signals are combined in a weighted manner in order to reduce noise, enhance contrast, diminish speckle artifacts, and produce a final image with improved sharpness and higher resolution.

Fig. 3. Frequency Compounding. Adapted from Ali et al. [7].

Once the signals have been processed and converted into visual information, it is necessary to define the most appropriate imaging mode for the diagnostic purpose. The following section presents the main image formation modes used in ultrasonography.

D. Modes of Image Formation

As described by Neumann and Kollorz [8], the processing of ultrasonic signals captured by the transducer can be carried out in different imaging modes, depending on the clinical objective. Several display modes are available, among which the four most fundamental will be highlighted:

- **A-mode (Amplitude Mode)** Represents the most basic mode, displaying data collected by the transducer in a single direction over time. As a result, this mode has a significant limitation due to its one-dimensional data presentation, but it remains useful for extracting key measurements such as frequency, wave phase, and attenuation.
- **B-mode (Brightness Mode)** This is the most widely used technique, as it allows the composition of multiple A-mode scans to create real-time two-dimensional

images. This is achieved by using mechanical or electronic scanning methods and transducers that capture signals from different angles to determine the intensity of each pixel.

- **M-mode (Motion Mode)** This technique involves rapidly emitting ultrasonic pulses without moving the transducer, aiming to generate successive images that enable the evaluation of motion. In this process, both A-mode and B-mode can be applied to each pulse, allowing the recording of the position of structures as a function of time. This method is widely used in cardiac ultrasonography.
- **Doppler Mode** This mode utilizes the Doppler Effect — the phenomenon of perceived frequency change due to relative motion between the source and the observer — to determine the direction and velocity of blood flow. The transducer is positioned at an angle, aiming for the smallest possible angle relative to the flow to enhance accuracy, as illustrated in Figure 4. Ultrasonic emissions can be emitted as either pulsed or continuous. The continuous emission mode allows for continuous measurements, whereas the pulsed mode is used for measuring distances.

Fig. 4. Doppler Formation Mode Application. Adapted from Neumann and Kollorz [8]

These four techniques represent the main image formation modes in ultrasonography and are chosen according to the diagnostic objective. A-mode, although simple, is important to ensure precision; B-mode is widely used to provide two-dimensional images useful for most cases; M-mode stands out for allowing motion analysis; and Doppler is most indicated for investigating blood flow. Therefore, each method contributes to the significant relevance of ultrasonography in diagnostic practice.

E. Advances in Image Post-Processing Techniques

In order to provide more accurate diagnoses, ultrasound images undergo additional post-processing that adjusts variables such as contrast and brightness to highlight specific structures.

In addition, new approaches are emerging that enable different forms of image presentation through automated processing, with the goal of correcting potential intrinsic errors from the imaging devices themselves and enhancing diagnostic quality.

In this context, the study conducted by Nahas et al. [9], which employs artificial intelligence (AI) techniques and parallel processing using Graphics Processing Units (GPUs), stands out as a significant innovation in image

processing. In this approach, ultrasound images used for visualizing blood flow—often affected by aliasing artifacts—can be computationally corrected based on the Doppler effect patterns caused by such inaccuracies.

Another ultrasound image post-processing technique that emerges as a promising innovation is phase modulation during beamforming, as proposed by Jing and Lindsey [10]. In their study, an improvement in the lateral resolution of the images was observed by applying small intentional phase errors, followed by subtracting the image based on the variability between the aberrated versions.

In addition to these approaches, a distinct method developed in the study by Venkatayogi et al. [11] introduces a novel image formation strategy. The work presents a technique called Short-Lag Spatial Coherence Imaging (SLSC), which analyzes the spatial coherence of the signals captured by the ultrasound system using dedicated GPUs. Since solid and fluid masses reflect acoustic waves differently, this technique stands out for its ability to identify benign cysts and distinguish them from calcifications, which may progress and develop into malignant tumors.

Therefore, it is evident that image processing techniques play a fundamental role in achieving more accurate diagnoses. New technologies are emerging with the goal of enhancing ultrasound image quality, fostering more effective medical care by integrating technological advances into clinical practice.

IV. CONCLUSION

Image reconstruction in ultrasonography is essential for generating accurate visual representations and is a determining factor in the diagnostic quality of this imaging modality. The fidelity of the resulting image directly impacts the ability to identify and characterize anatomical structures and potential pathological changes, which is crucial in clinical practice.

This process begins with the emission and reception of ultrasonic waves by piezoelectric transducers, followed by beamforming, which spatially focuses the acoustic energy. From the echoes reflected by tissues, signals are temporally aligned and summed, forming the basis of the ultrasound image. Traditional methods, such as Delay-and-Sum, are still widely used due to their simplicity and efficiency. However, more recent techniques, based on spatial coherence and adaptive algorithms, have gained prominence for offering better resolution and artifact reduction, highlighting the potential of image reconstruction as a continually evolving field.

In conclusion, image reconstruction in ultrasonography is an area of ongoing development, driven by advancements in engineering. The integration of theoretical foundations with computational solutions has expanded diagnostic possibilities, making this modality increasingly effective and accurate in clinical practice.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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